

Promoting Inclusion in COVID-19 Research for Diverse Hispanic/Latino(x) Populations: 5 Recommendations

Including Hispanic/Latino(x) populations in COVID-19 research is necessary to ensure this population benefits from biomedical and public health advances.

- 1. Ensure government-supported websites for research measures can be accessible** in Spanish and Indigenous languages spoken by diverse Hispanic/Latino(x) communities

- 2. Support the dissemination of field-adapted and validated measures** for diverse Hispanic/Latino(x) communities

- 3. Invest in translating and validating research measures in Spanish,** particularly those developed in the field by community health workers or other members of the community

- 4. Increase funding for pathway programs, career development grants, and diversity awards** to support bilingual/bicultural research workforce

- 5. Remove barriers for Hispanic/Latino(x) participation** in COVID-19 testing and research, such as removing requirements for identification, insurance, and disclosing social security numbers

These recommendations created by the RADx-UP Hispanic/Latino(x) Working Group can guide the implementation of policies and practices to improve the engagement of institutions with this population and conduct research on current health disparities and future health crises with a lens of health equity.